

RT² Profiler PCR Array Gene Expression Analysis Report

Shafeeq Mohammed

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Introduction

Cataloged arrays

RT² Profiler PCR Arrays are highly reliable and sensitive gene expression profiling tools for analyzing focused panels of genes in signal transduction, biological processes or disease research pathways using real-time PCR. Each cataloged RT² Profiler PCR Array contains a list of the pathway-focused genes as well as five housekeeping (reference) genes on the array. In addition, each array contains a panel of proprietary controls to monitor genomic DNA contamination (GDC) as well as the first strand synthesis (RTC) and real-time PCR efficiency (PPC). The qPCR Assays used in PCR Arrays are laboratory-verified and optimized to work under standard conditions enabling a large number of genes to be assayed simultaneously. Their specificity is guaranteed when RT² SYBR Green qPCR Master Mixes are used as part of the complete PCR Array System protocol.

In this study, 96 genes were profiled on 16 samples with the PAHS-024Z.

Summary and workflow

Cataloged arrays

1. Mature RNA was isolated using an RNA extraction kit according to the manufacturer's instructions.
2. RNA quality was determined using a spectrophotometer and was reverse transcribed using a cDNA conversion kit.
3. The cDNA was used on the real-time RT² Profiler PCR Array (QIAGEN, Cat. no. PAHS-024Z) in combination with RT² SYBR® Green qPCR Mastermix (Cat. no. 330529).

C_T values were exported to an Excel file to create a table of C_T values. This table was then uploaded on to the data analysis web portal at <http://www.qiagen.com/geneglobe>. Samples were assigned to controls and test groups. C_T values were normalized based on a/an Manual Selection of reference genes.

The data analysis web portal calculates fold change/regulation using delta delta C_T method, in which delta C_T is calculated between gene of interest (GOI) and an average of reference genes (HKG), followed by delta-delta C_T calculations (delta C_T (Test Group)-delta C_T (Control Group)). Fold Change is then calculated using $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$ formula. The data analysis web portal also plots scatter plot, volcano plot, clustergram, and heat map.

This data analysis report was exported from the QIAGEN web portal at GeneGlobe.

Gene Table

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
A01	NM_005163	AKT1	V-akt murine thymoma viral oncogene homolog 1
A02	NM_001145	ANG	Angiogenin, ribonuclease, RNase A family, 5
A03	NM_001146	ANGPT1	Angiopoietin 1
A04	NM_001147	ANGPT2	Angiopoietin 2
A05	NM_001039667	ANGPTL4	Angiopoietin-like 4
A06	NM_001150	ANPEP	Alanyl (membrane) aminopeptidase
A07	NM_001702	ADGRB1	Brain-specific angiogenesis inhibitor 1
A08	NM_002986	CCL11	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 11
A09	NM_002982	CCL2	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 2
A10	NM_001795	CDH5	Cadherin 5, type 2 (vascular endothelium)
A11	NM_030582	COL18A1	Collagen, type XVIII, alpha 1
A12	NM_000091	COL4A3	Collagen, type IV, alpha 3 (Goodpasture antigen)
B01	NM_001901	CTGF	Connective tissue growth factor
B02	NM_001511	CXCL1	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 1 (melanoma growth stimulating activity, alpha)
B03	NM_001565	CXCL10	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 10
B04	NM_002994	CXCL5	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 5
B05	NM_002993	CXCL6	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 6 (granulocyte chemotactic protein 2)
B06	NM_002416	CXCL9	Chemokine (C-X-C motif) ligand 9
B07	NM_001955	EDN1	Endothelin 1
B08	NM_182685	EFNA1	Ephrin-A1
B09	NM_004093	EFNB2	Ephrin-B2
B10	NM_001963	EGF	Epidermal growth factor
B11	NM_000118	ENG	Endoglin
B12	NM_004444	EPHB4	EPH receptor B4
C01	NM_004448	ERBB2	V-erb-b2 erythroblastic leukemia viral oncogene homolog 2, neuro/glioblastoma derived oncogene homolog (avian)
C02	NM_001993	F3	Coagulation factor III (thromboplastin, tissue factor)
C03	NM_000800	FGF1	Fibroblast growth factor 1 (acidic)
C04	NM_002006	FGF2	Fibroblast growth factor 2 (basic)
C05	NM_000142	FGFR3	Fibroblast growth factor receptor 3
C06	NM_004469	FIGF	C-fos induced growth factor (vascular endothelial growth factor D)
C07	NM_002019	FLT1	Fms-related tyrosine kinase 1 (vascular endothelial growth factor/vascular permeability factor receptor)
C08	NM_002026	FN1	Fibronectin 1
C09	NM_000601	HGF	Hepatocyte growth factor (hepapoietin A; scatter factor)
C10	NM_001530	HIF1A	Hypoxia inducible factor 1, alpha subunit (basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor)

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
C11	NM_006665	HPSE	Heparanase
C12	NM_002165	ID1	Inhibitor of DNA binding 1, dominant negative helix-loop-helix protein
D01	NM_024013	IFNA1	Interferon, alpha 1
D02	NM_000619	IFNG	Interferon, gamma
D03	NM_000618	IGF1	Insulin-like growth factor 1 (somatomedin C)
D04	NM_000576	IL1B	Interleukin 1, beta
D05	NM_000600	IL6	Interleukin 6 (interferon, beta 2)
D06	NM_000584	CXCL8	Interleukin 8
D07	NM_002210	ITGAV	Integrin, alpha V (vitronectin receptor, alpha polypeptide, antigen CD51)
D08	NM_000212	ITGB3	Integrin, beta 3 (platelet glycoprotein IIIa, antigen CD61)
D09	NM_000214	JAG1	Jagged 1
D10	NM_002253	KDR	Kinase insert domain receptor (a type III receptor tyrosine kinase)
D11	NM_007015	LECT1	Leukocyte cell derived chemotaxin 1
D12	NM_000230	LEP	Leptin
E01	NM_002391	MDK	Midkine (neurite growth-promoting factor 2)
E02	NM_004995	MMP14	Matrix metalloproteinase 14 (membrane-inserted)
E03	NM_004530	MMP2	Matrix metalloproteinase 2 (gelatinase A, 72kDa gelatinase, 72kDa type IV collagenase)
E04	NM_004994	MMP9	Matrix metalloproteinase 9 (gelatinase B, 92kDa gelatinase, 92kDa type IV collagenase)
E05	NM_000603	NOS3	Nitric oxide synthase 3 (endothelial cell)
E06	NM_004557	NOTCH4	Notch 4
E07	NM_003873	NRP1	Neuropilin 1
E08	NM_003872	NRP2	Neuropilin 2
E09	NM_002607	PDGFA	Platelet-derived growth factor alpha polypeptide
E10	NM_000442	PECAM1	Platelet/endothelial cell adhesion molecule
E11	NM_002619	PF4	Platelet factor 4
E12	NM_002632	PGF	Placental growth factor
F01	NM_002658	PLAU	Plasminogen activator, urokinase
F02	NM_000301	PLG	Plasminogen
F03	NM_021935	PROK2	Prokineticin 2
F04	NM_000962	PTGS1	Prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 1 (prostaglandin G/H synthase and cyclooxygenase)
F05	NM_001400	S1PR1	Sphingosine-1-phosphate receptor 1
F06	NM_000602	SERPINE1	Serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade E (nexin, plasminogen activator inhibitor type 1), member 1
F07	NM_002615	SERPINF1	Serpin peptidase inhibitor, clade F (alpha-2 antiplasmin, pigment epithelium derived factor), member 1
F08	NM_021972	SPHK1	Sphingosine kinase 1
F09	NM_000459	TEK	TEK tyrosine kinase, endothelial
F10	NM_003236	TGFA	Transforming growth factor, alpha
F11	NM_000660	TGFB1	Transforming growth factor, beta 1

Position	RefSeq Number	Symbol	Description
F12	NM_003238	TGFB2	Transforming growth factor, beta 2
G01	NM_004612	TGFBR1	Transforming growth factor, beta receptor 1
G02	NM_003246	THBS1	Thrombospondin 1
G03	NM_003247	THBS2	Thrombospondin 2
G04	NM_005424	TIE1	Tyrosine kinase with immunoglobulin-like and EGF-like domains 1
G05	NM_003254	TIMP1	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 1
G06	NM_003255	TIMP2	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 2
G07	NM_000362	TIMP3	TIMP metalloproteinase inhibitor 3
G08	NM_000594	TNF	Tumor necrosis factor
G09	NM_001953	TYMP	Thymidine phosphorylase
G10	NM_003376	VEGFA	Vascular endothelial growth factor A
G11	NM_003377	VEGFB	Vascular endothelial growth factor B
G12	NM_005429	VEGFC	Vascular endothelial growth factor C
H01	NM_001101	ACTB	Actin, beta
H02	NM_004048	B2M	Beta-2-microglobulin
H03	NM_002046	GAPDH	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
H04	NM_000194	HPRT1	Hypoxanthine phosphoribosyltransferase 1
H05	NM_001002	RPLP0	Ribosomal protein, large, P0
H06	SA_00105	HGDC	Human Genomic DNA Contamination
H07	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H08	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H09	SA_00104	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H10	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H11	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H12	SA_00103	PPC	Positive PCR Control

Data analysis setup

Sample management

Sample ID	Sample Name	Group
1	NG	Control Group
2	NG.1	Control Group
3	NG.2	Control Group
4	NG.3	Control Group
5	HG	Group 1
6	HG.1	Group 1
7	HG.2	Group 1
8	HG.3	Group 1
9	HG + RVX208	Group 2
10	HG + RVX208.1	Group 2
11	HG + RVX208.2	Group 2
12	HG + RVX208.3	Group 2
13	HG + DMSO	Group 3
14	HG + DMSO.1	Group 3
15	HG + DMSO.2	Group 3
16	HG + DMSO.3	Group 3

Pre-amplification

A pre-amplification using the appropriate species- and pathway-specific RT² PreAMP Primer Mix was performed and the appropriate corrections were made during the data analysis procedure.

Lower limit of detection

The C_T cut-off was set to 35

Data quality control (QC)

Quality checks performed and results

Test Performed	Test Result
1. PCR Array Reproducibility	All Samples Passed
2. Reverse Transcription Efficiency	All Samples Passed
3. Genomic DNA Contamination	All Samples Passed

Normalization analysis

Manual Selection

Groups	Samples	ACTB	B2M	GAPDH	HPRT1	RPLP0	Arithmetic Mean	Average Arithmetic Mean
Control Group	NG	18.79	21.86	19.84	26.63	19.43	21.31	20.90
Control Group	NG.1	18.57	21.65	19.61	26.39	19.09	21.06	
Control Group	NG.2	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	19.93	
Control Group	NG.3	18.79	21.86	19.84	26.63	19.43	21.31	
Group 1	HG	18.65	21.61	19.69	26.51	19.42	21.18	20.56
Group 1	HG.1	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	
Group 1	HG.2	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	19.95	
Group 1	HG.3	18.65	21.61	19.69	26.51	19.42	21.18	
Group 2	HG + RVX208	20.35	22.10	20.98	27.51	19.98	22.18	21.79
Group 2	HG + RVX208.1	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	
Group 2	HG + RVX208.2	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	21.40	
Group 2	HG + RVX208.3	20.35	22.10	20.98	27.51	19.98	22.18	
Group 3	HG + DMSO	19.12	21.71	20.06	26.54	19.85	21.45	21.06
Group 3	HG + DMSO.1	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	
Group 3	HG + DMSO.2	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	20.67	
Group 3	HG + DMSO.3	19.12	21.71	20.06	26.54	19.85	21.45	

In the Manual Selection method, the arithmetic or geometric means of the data from the assays for the housekeeping / reference genes listed in the table were used to normalize the raw data.

Result

Fold regulation and p-value

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2	0.05

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments
A06	ANPEP	2.30	0.000174	
A07	ADGRB1	2.11	0.041037	
A12	COL4A3	2.64	0.009831	
B03	CXCL10	2.41	0.000007	
B06	CXCL9	4.47	0.000405	
C03	FGF1	2.34	0.025053	C
C05	FGFR3	2.76	0.000092	
C12	ID1	2.32	0.000000	
D02	IFNG	2.34	0.025053	C
D11	LECT1	2.34	0.025053	C
E05	NOS3	3.76	0.003773	
F02	PLG	2.34	0.025053	C
F03	PROK2	2.34	0.025053	C
G10	VEGFA	8.23	0.003096	
A02	ANG	-2.13	0.000008	A
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	0.000003	A
A09	CCL2	-33.55	0.000015	
B02	CXCL1	-6.22	0.000008	
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	0.000001	A
C06	FIGF	-2.72	0.000004	
C08	FN1	-2.23	0.000043	
D03	IGF1	-4.09	0.000441	
D04	IL1B	-3.31	0.048571	
D05	IL6	-4.30	0.007952	A
D06	CXCL8	-11.41	0.000000	
E02	MMP14	-2.63	0.000082	
E06	NOTCH4	-2.80	0.000019	
E07	NRP1	-2.78	0.003133	
E12	PGF	-2.52	0.000854	
F01	PLAU	-2.33	0.000006	
F04	PTGS1	-2.22	0.000018	
F08	SPHK1	-3.96	0.000161	

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments
F10	TGFA	-2.75	0.000000	
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	0.002926	A
G02	THBS1	-5.35	0.000355	

Fold-Change ($2^{(-\Delta\Delta C_T)}$) is the normalized gene expression ($2^{(-\Delta C_T)}$) in the Test Sample divided the normalized gene expression ($2^{(-\Delta C_T)}$) in the Control Sample. Fold-Regulation represents fold-change results in a biologically meaningful way. Fold-change values greater than one indicates a positive- or an up-regulation, and the fold-regulation is equal to the fold-change. Fold-change values less than one indicate a negative or down-regulation, and the fold-regulation is the negative inverse of the fold-change.

The p values are calculated based on a Student's t-test of the replicate $2^{(-\Delta C_T)}$ values for each gene in the control group and treatment groups, and p values less than 0.05 are indicated in red. The p-value calculation used is based on parametric, unpaired, two-sample equal variance, two-tailed distribution – a method widely accepted in scientific literature.

Scatter Plot

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2

The Scatter Plot compares the normalized expression of every gene on the PCR Array between the two selected groups by plotting them against one another to quickly visualize large gene expression changes. The center diagonal line indicates unchanged gene expression, while the outer diagonal lines indicate the selected fold regulation threshold. Genes with data points beyond the outer lines in the upper left and lower right corners are up-regulated or down-regulated, respectively, by more than the fold regulation threshold in the y-axis Group relative to the x-axis Group.

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A03	ANGPT1	2.34	B	PPH00374B
A06	ANPEP	2.30		PPH05672A
A07	ADGRB1	2.11		PPH01351E
A12	COL4A3	2.64		PPH02131C
B03	CXCL10	2.41		PPH00765E
B06	CXCL9	4.47		PPH00700B
B10	EGF	23429.99	A	PPH00137B
C03	FGF1	2.34	C	PPH00067F
C05	FGFR3	2.76		PPH00382A
C12	ID1	2.32		PPH00317B
D02	IFNG	2.34	C	PPH00380C
D11	LECT1	2.34	C	PPH19892A
E05	NOS3	3.76		PPH01298F
F02	PLG	2.34	C	PPH02587G
F03	PROK2	2.34	C	PPH24188A
G10	VEGFA	8.23		PPH00251C

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A02	ANG	-2.13	A	PPH00376A
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	A	PPH00377F
A09	CCL2	-33.55		PPH00192F
B02	CXCL1	-6.22		PPH00696C
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	A	PPH00704B
C06	FIGF	-2.72		PPH00624A
C08	FN1	-2.23		PPH00143B
D03	IGF1	-4.09		PPH00167C
D04	IL1B	-3.31		PPH00171C
D05	IL6	-4.30	A	PPH00560C
D06	CXCL8	-11.41		PPH00568A
E02	MMP14	-2.63		PPH00198C
E06	NOTCH4	-2.80		PPH06021F
E07	NRP1	-2.78		PPH01152A
E12	PGF	-2.52		PPH01155F
F01	PLAU	-2.33		PPH00796C
F04	PTGS1	-2.22		PPH01306F
F08	SPHK1	-3.96		PPH02491A
F10	TGFA	-2.75		PPH00378B
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	A	PPH00524B
G02	THBS1	-5.35		PPH00799F

Volcano Plot

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2	0.05

Group 2 vs. Group 1

The Volcano Plot identifies significant gene expression changes by plotting the $\log_2$ of the fold changes in gene expression on the x-axis versus their statistical significance on the y-axis. The center vertical line indicates unchanged gene expression, while the two outer vertical lines indicate the selected fold regulation threshold. The horizontal line indicates the selected p-value threshold. Genes with data points in the far upper left (down-regulated) and far upper right (up-regulated) sections meet the selected fold regulation and p-value thresholds. By combining the fold change results with the p-value statistical test results, genes with both large and small expression changes that are statistically significant are easily visualized.

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A03	ANGPT1	2.34	0.060192	B	PPH00374B
A06	ANPEP	2.30	0.000174		PPH05672A
A07	ADGRB1	2.11	0.041037		PPH01351E
A12	COL4A3	2.64	0.009831		PPH02131C
B03	CXCL10	2.41	0.000007		PPH00765E
B06	CXCL9	4.47	0.000405		PPH00700B
B10	EGF	23429.99	0.133975	A	PPH00137B
C03	FGF1	2.34	0.025053	C	PPH00067F
C05	FGFR3	2.76	0.000092		PPH00382A
C12	ID1	2.32	0.000000		PPH00317B
D02	IFNG	2.34	0.025053	C	PPH00380C
D11	LECT1	2.34	0.025053	C	PPH19892A
E05	NOS3	3.76	0.003773		PPH01298F
F02	PLG	2.34	0.025053	C	PPH02587G
F03	PROK2	2.34	0.025053	C	PPH24188A
G10	VEGFA	8.23	0.003096		PPH00251C

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	Comments	RT ² qPCR Assay Catalog #
A02	ANG	-2.13	0.000008	A	PPH00376A
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	0.000003	A	PPH00377F
A09	CCL2	-33.55	0.000015		PPH00192F
B02	CXCL1	-6.22	0.000008		PPH00696C
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	0.000001	A	PPH00704B
C06	FIGF	-2.72	0.000004		PPH00624A
C08	FN1	-2.23	0.000043		PPH00143B
D03	IGF1	-4.09	0.000441		PPH00167C
D04	IL1B	-3.31	0.048571		PPH00171C
D05	IL6	-4.30	0.007952	A	PPH00560C
D06	CXCL8	-11.41	0.000000		PPH00568A
E02	MMP14	-2.63	0.000082		PPH00198C
E06	NOTCH4	-2.80	0.000019		PPH06021F
E07	NRP1	-2.78	0.003133		PPH01152A
E12	PGF	-2.52	0.000854		PPH01155F
F01	PLAU	-2.33	0.000006		PPH00796C
F04	PTGS1	-2.22	0.000018		PPH01306F
F08	SPHK1	-3.96	0.000161		PPH02491A
F10	TGFA	-2.75	0.000000		PPH00378B
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	0.002926	A	PPH00524B
G02	THBS1	-5.35	0.000355		PPH00799F

Clustergram

Sample	Dimension	Join Type	Color Coded
Array	2-D	Average	Genes

Heat Map

Test Group	Control Group
Group 2	Group 1

Visualization of log2(Fold Change)

Layout	01	02	03	04	05	06	07	08	09	10	11	12
A	AKT1 / -1.04	ANG / -2.13 / A	ANGPT1 / 2.34 / B	ANGPT2 / -2.64 / A	ANGPTL4 / 1.02	ANPEP / 2.3	ADGRB1 / 2.11	CCL11 / 1.3 / B	CCL2 / -33.55	CDH5 / -1.42	COL18A1 / -1.14	COL4A3 / 2.64
B	CTGF / 1.09	CXCL1 / -6.22	CXCL10 / 2.41	CXCL5 / -1.77 / B	CXCL6 / -9.41 / A	CXCL9 / 4.47	EDN1 / -1.09	EFNA1 / -1.46	EFNB2 / -1.0	EGF / 23429.99 / A	ENG / 1.7	EPHB4 / -1.06
C	ERBB2 / -1.13	F3 / -1.78	FGF1 / 2.34 / C	FGF2 / -1.35	FGFR3 / 2.76	FIGF / -2.72	FLT1 / 1.55	FN1 / -2.23	HGF / 1.58 / B	HIF1A / -1.44	HPSE / 1.16	ID1 / 2.32
D	IFNA1 / -1.21 / B	IFNG / 2.34 / C	IGF1 / -4.09	IL1B / -3.31	IL6 / -4.3 / A	CXCL8 / -11.41	ITGAV / -1.93	ITGB3 / 1.43	JAG1 / -1.08	KDR / -1.1	LECT1 / 2.34 / C	LEP / 1.41
E	MDK / -1.35	MMP14 / -2.63	MMP2 / -1.17	MMP9 / -1.43 / B	NOS3 / 3.76	NOTCH4 / -2.8	NRP1 / -2.78	NRP2 / 1.09	PDGFA / -1.03	PECAM1 / 1.8	PF4 / 1.43 / B	PGF / -2.52
F	PLAU / -2.33	PLG / 2.34 / C	PROK2 / 2.34 / C	PTGS1 / -2.22	S1PR1 / -1.2	SERPINE1 / 1.28	SERPINF1 / -1.07 / B	SPHK1 / -3.96	TEK / -1.56	TGFA / -2.75	TGFB1 / 1.5	TGFB2 / -26.16 / A
G	TGFBRI / -1.54	THBS1 / -5.35	THBS2 / -1.08 / B	TIE1 / -1.42	TIMP1 / 1.12	TIMP2 / 1.56	TIMP3 / 1.97	TNF / 1.61 / B	TYMP / -1.35	VEGFA / 8.23	VEGFB / -1.14	VEGFC / -1.85

What's next

Thank you for using the RT² Profiler Data Analysis Software.

The Data Analysis software delivers a list of expression changes in the samples from the supplied data. However, this result often only starts an investigation into the underlying mechanisms at work. In order to assist in further analysis, the QIAGEN now utilizes the latest bioinformatics tools to analyze the data and suggest regulatory mechanisms and future experiments. Please review the results from the selected tools below.

Gene Expression: This tool will help define a panel of genes based of this experiment's results. This panel may represent a putative biomarker set, a target gene set or simply a collection of genes. The tool is designed to deliver a list of gene expression assays that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

miRNA Regulation: This tool will identify candidate miRNA regulators in your experimental system. The tool is designed to deliver a list of miRNAs that could be targeting the genes that had observed changes in expression in your selected samples.

DNA Methylation: This tool will help define a panel of differentially expressed genes based on this experiment's results. Altered methylation patterns on the genes' promoters may be responsible for these gene expression changes. This tool is designed to deliver a list of available DNA methylation assays for those differentially expressed genes that would allow the user to follow-up their gene expression experiment with an epigenetic analysis.

Transcription Factor / Histone: This tool will help define a panel of differentially expressed genes based on this experiment's results. Altered transcription factor binding activity on the genes' promoters may be responsible for these gene expression changes. Altered histone modification patterns on the genes' promoters may also be responsible for these gene expression changes. This tool is designed to deliver a list of the transcription factors that might regulate the selected differentially expressed genes as well as the available respective gene-specific real-time PCR assays for DNA from anti-transcription factor or anti-histone chromatin immunoprecipitations. These assays would then allow the user to follow-up their gene expression experiment with an epigenetic analysis.

Protein Detection: This tool will help define a panel of cytokines or chemokines based on this experiment's results. This panel may represent a putative biomarker set, a target gene set or simply a collection of genes. The tool is designed to deliver a list of ELISAs that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

Somatic Mutation: This tool will help define a panel of genes based on this experiment's results. Mutations in these genes may affect whether their expression changes have any effect or different effects on the experimental model system. The tool is designed to deliver a list of available somatic mutation assays for these differentially expressed genes that would allow the user to follow-up the results of the analyzed experiment.

Gene Expression, DNA Methylation, Protein Detection, Somatic Mutation

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2	0.05

Position	Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	RT2 qPCR Assay	EpiTect Methyl II qPCR Assay	Single Analyte ELISArray	Somatic Mutation Assay
A06	ANPEP	2.3	0.000174	PPH05672A	EPHS104797-1A		
A07	ADGRB1	2.11	0.041037	PPH01351E	EPHS114085-1A		
A12	COL4A3	2.64	0.009831	PPH02131C	EPHS108922-1A		
B03	CXCL10	2.41	7e-06	PPH00765E		SEH00765A	
B06	CXCL9	4.47	0.000405	PPH00700B		SEH00700A	
C03	FGF1	2.34	0.025053	PPH00067F			
C05	FGFR3	2.76	9.2e-05	PPH00382A	EPHS110859-1A		SMPH005549A
C12	ID1	2.32	0.0	PPH00317B	EPHS109178-1A		
D02	IFNG	2.34	0.025053	PPH00380C		SEH00380A	
D11	LECT1	2.34	0.025053	PPH19892A	EPHS103787-1A		
E05	NOS3	3.76	0.003773	PPH01298F			
F02	PLG	2.34	0.025053	PPH02587G			
F03	PROK2	2.34	0.025053	PPH24188A	EPHS110392-1A		
G10	VEGFA	8.23	0.003096	PPH00251C	EPHS112506-1A		
A02	ANG	-2.13	8e-06	PPH00376A	EPHS103917-1A		
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	3e-06	PPH00377F			
A09	CCL2	-33.55	1.5e-05	PPH00192F		SEH00192A	
B02	CXCL1	-6.22	8e-06	PPH00696C	EPHS111074-1A	SEH00696A	
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	1e-06	PPH00704B	EPHS111072-1A		
C06	FIGF	-2.72	4e-06	PPH00624A			
C08	FN1	-2.23	4.3e-05	PPH00143B	EPHS108848-1A		
D03	IGF1	-4.09	0.000441	PPH00167C			
D04	IL1B	-3.31	0.048571	PPH00171C		SEH00171A	
D05	IL6	-4.3	0.007952	PPH00560C		SEH00560A	
D06	CXCL8	-11.41	0.0	PPH00568A			
E02	MMP14	-2.63	8.2e-05	PPH00198C	EPHS103936-1A		
E06	NOTCH4	-2.8	1.9e-05	PPH06021F			
E07	NRP1	-2.78	0.003133	PPH01152A	EPHS101560-1A		
E12	PGF	-2.52	0.000854	PPH01155F	EPHS104212-1A		
F01	PLAU	-2.33	6e-06	PPH00796C	EPHS101714-1A		
F04	PTGS1	-2.22	1.8e-05	PPH01306F			
F08	SPHK1	-3.96	0.000161	PPH02491A	EPHS106358-1A		
F10	TGFA	-2.75	0.0	PPH00378B	EPHS108297-1A		

Position	Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	RT2 qPCR Assay	EpiTect Methyl II qPCR Assay	Single Analyte ELISArray	Somatic Mutation Assay
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	0.002926	PPH00524B	EPHS101278-1A		
G02	THBS1	-5.35	0.000355	PPH00799F	EPHS104439-1A		

miRNA Regulation

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2	0.05

Genes Under-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value
A02	ANG	-2.13	0.000008
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	0.000003
A09	CCL2	-33.55	0.000015
B02	CXCL1	-6.22	0.000008
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	0.000001
C06	FIGF	-2.72	0.000004
C08	FN1	-2.23	0.000043
D03	IGF1	-4.09	0.000441
D04	IL1B	-3.31	0.048571
D05	IL6	-4.30	0.007952
D06	CXCL8	-11.41	0.000000
E02	MMP14	-2.63	0.000082
E06	NOTCH4	-2.80	0.000019
E07	NRP1	-2.78	0.003133
E12	PGF	-2.52	0.000854
F01	PLAU	-2.33	0.000006
F04	PTGS1	-2.22	0.000018
F08	SPHK1	-3.96	0.000161
F10	TGFA	-2.75	0.000000
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	0.002926
G02	THBS1	-5.35	0.000355

miRNA Regulating Genes Under-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-130a-3p	-0.22	MS00003444	MSY0000425	MIN0000425	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-130b-3p	-0.22	MS00003451	MSY0000691	MIN0000691	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-301a-3p	-0.23	MS00009317	MSY0000688	MIN0000688	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-301b	-0.25	MS00009324	MSY0004958	MIN0004958	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-374a-5p	-0.33	MS00009604	MSY0000727	MIN0000727	CCL2,TGFA,MMP14
hsa-miR-374b-5p	-0.30	MS00009618	MSY0004955	MIN0004955	CCL2,TGFA,MMP14
hsa-miR-454-3p	-0.22	MS00007861	MSY0003885	MIN0003885	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-548c-3p	-0.09	MS00010122	MSY0003285	MIN0003285	IGF1,PLAU,MMP14

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-1	-0.28	MS00008358	MSY0000416	MIN0000416	IGF1,NRP1,THBS1
hsa-miR-101-3p	-0.14	MS00008372	MSY0000099	MIN0000099	TGFA, FN1, THBS1
hsa-miR-1200	-0.04	MS00042392	MSY0005863	MIN0005863	PGF,NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-124-3p	-0.23	MS00006622	MSY0000422	MIN0000422	SPHK1,PGF,NRP1
hsa-miR-144-3p	-0.12	MS00020328	MSY0000436	MIN0000436	TGFA, FN1, THBS1
hsa-miR-148a-3p	-0.40	MS00003556	MSY0000243	MIN0000243	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-148b-3p	-0.40	MS00031458	MSY0000759	MIN0000759	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-152-3p	-0.40	MS00003591	MSY0000438	MIN0000438	IGF1,NRP1,TGFA
hsa-miR-181a-5p	-0.09	MS00008827	MSY0000256	MIN0000256	PLAU,NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-181b-5p	-0.09	MS00006699	MSY0000257	MIN0000257	PLAU,NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-181c-5p	-0.07	MS00008841	MSY0000258	MIN0000258	PLAU,NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-181d-5p	-0.09	MS00031500	MSY0002821	MIN0002821	PLAU,NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-206	-0.28	MS00003787	MSY0000462	MIN0000462	IGF1,NRP1,THBS1
hsa-miR-506-3p	-0.23	MS00009856	MSY0002878	MIN0002878	SPHK1,PGF,NRP1
hsa-miR-613	-0.25	MS00005054	MSY0003281	MIN0003281	IGF1,NRP1,THBS1
hsa-miR-1827	-0.06	MS00014686	MSY0006767	MIN0006767	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-186-5p	-0.01	MS00003654	MSY0000456	MIN0000456	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-let-7a-5p	-0.16	MS00031220	MSY0000062	MIN0000062	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7b-5p	-0.16	MS00003122	MSY0000063	MIN0000063	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7c-5p	-0.16	MS00003129	MSY0000064	MIN0000064	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7d-5p	-0.16	MS00003136	MSY0000065	MIN0000065	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7e-5p	-0.16	MS00031227	MSY0000066	MIN0000066	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7f-5p	-0.16	MS00006489	MSY0000067	MIN0000067	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7g-5p	-0.16	MS00008337	MSY0000414	MIN0000414	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-let-7i-5p	-0.16	MS00003157	MSY0000415	MIN0000415	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-1297	0.00	MS00031374	MSY0005886	MIN0005886	IGF1,MMP14
hsa-miR-137	-0.15	MS00003486	MSY0000429	MIN0000429	TGFA,NRP1
hsa-miR-141-3p	-0.37	MS00003507	MSY0000432	MIN0000432	NRP1,TGFB2
hsa-miR-182-5p	-0.14	MS00008855	MSY0000259	MIN0000259	FN1,FIGF
hsa-miR-194-5p	-0.18	MS00006727	MSY0000460	MIN0000460	NRP1,THBS1
hsa-miR-199a-3p	-0.12	MS00007602	MSY0000232	MIN0000232	IGF1, FN1
hsa-miR-199b-3p	-0.12	MS00007602	MSY0004563	MIN0004563	IGF1, FN1
hsa-miR-19a-3p	-0.27	MS00003192	MSY0000073	MIN0000073	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-19b-3p	-0.27	MS00031584	MSY0000074	MIN0000074	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-200a-3p	-0.37	MS00003738	MSY0000682	MIN0000682	NRP1,TGFB2
hsa-miR-202-3p	-0.07	MS00009037	MSY0002811	MIN0002811	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-221-3p	-0.16	MS00003857	MSY0000278	MIN0000278	IGF1,THBS1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-222-3p	-0.16	MS00007609	MSY0000279	MIN0000279	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-23a-3p	-0.30	MS00031633	MSY0000078	MIN0000078	PLAU,TGFA
hsa-miR-23b-3p	-0.32	MS00031647	MSY0000418	MIN0000418	PLAU,TGFA
hsa-miR-24-3p	-0.14	MS00006552	MSY0000080	MIN0000080	NRP1,MMP14
hsa-miR-26a-5p	0.00	MS00029239	MSY0000082	MIN0000082	IGF1,MMP14
hsa-miR-26b-5p	0.00	MS00003234	MSY0000083	MIN0000083	IGF1,MMP14
hsa-miR-320a	-0.15	MS00014707	MSY0000510	MIN0000510	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-320b	-0.15	MS00031703	MSY0005792	MIN0005792	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-320c	-0.15	MS00041867	MSY0005793	MIN0005793	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-320d	-0.15	MS00031710	MSY0006764	MIN0006764	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-338-3p	-0.10	MS00003990	MSY0000763	MIN0000763	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-377-3p	0.04	MS00004095	MSY0000730	MIN0000730	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-410-3p	-0.16	MS00004144	MSY0002171	MIN0002171	IGF1,MMP14
hsa-miR-513b-5p	-0.21	MS00009919	MSY0005788	MIN0005788	NRP1,FIGF
hsa-miR-539-5p	-0.04	MS00004578	MSY0003163	MIN0003163	NRP1,ANGPT2
hsa-miR-542-3p	-0.20	MS00010073	MSY0003389	MIN0003389	ANGPT2,FIGF
hsa-miR-590-3p	-0.14	MS00010269	MSY0004801	MIN0004801	IGF1,TGFA
hsa-miR-607	-0.13	MS00005012	MSY0003275	MIN0003275	IGF1,NOTCH4
hsa-miR-641	-0.16	MS00032067	MSY0003311	MIN0003311	CXCL6,CXCL1
hsa-miR-758-3p	-0.16	MS00010563	MSY0003879	MIN0003879	IGF1,ANGPT2
hsa-miR-9-5p	-0.05	MS00010752	MSY0000441	MIN0000441	IGF1,NRP1
hsa-miR-944	-0.24	MS00010899	MSY0004987	MIN0004987	THBS1,MMP14
hsa-miR-98-5p	-0.16	MS00003367	MSY0000096	MIN0000096	IGF1,THBS1
hsa-miR-214-3p	-0.20	MS00031605	MSY0000271	MIN0000271	PGF
hsa-miR-29a-3p	-0.16	MS00003262	MSY0000086	MIN0000086	IGF1
hsa-miR-29b-3p	-0.16	MS00006566	MSY0000100	MIN0000100	IGF1
hsa-miR-29c-3p	-0.16	MS00003269	MSY0000681	MIN0000681	IGF1
hsa-miR-369-3p	-0.19	MS00006853	MSY0000721	MIN0000721	MMP14
hsa-miR-412-3p	-0.11	MS00004158	MSY0002170	MIN0002170	IGF1
hsa-miR-483-3p	0.00	MS00009751	MSY0002173	MIN0002173	IGF1
hsa-miR-495-3p	-0.16	MS00004347	MSY0002817	MIN0002817	IGF1
hsa-miR-519a-3p	-0.12	MS00033852	MSY0002869	MIN0002869	IGF1
hsa-miR-519b-3p	-0.12	MS00004501	MSY0002837	MIN0002837	IGF1
hsa-miR-519c-3p	-0.12	MS00010003	MSY0002832	MIN0002832	IGF1
hsa-miR-599	-0.22	MS00010297	MSY0003267	MIN0003267	IGF1
hsa-miR-1178-3p	-0.52	MS00014077	MSY0005823	MIN0005823	TGFA
hsa-miR-1202	-0.17	nan	MSY0005865	MIN0005865	MMP14

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-1206	-0.13	MS00014175	MSY0005870	MIN0005870	NRP1
hsa-miR-1207-5p	-0.23	MS00014189	MSY0005871	MIN0005871	IGF1
hsa-miR-1226-3p	-0.27	MS00008463	MSY0005577	MIN0005577	NRP1
hsa-miR-1243	-0.21	MS00014203	MSY0005894	MIN0005894	IGF1
hsa-miR-1244	-0.22	MS00031304	MSY0005896	MIN0005896	NRP1
hsa-miR-1251-5p	-0.24	MS00014259	MSY0005903	MIN0005903	IGF1
hsa-miR-1252-5p	-0.30	MS00031318	MSY0005944	MIN0005944	IGF1
hsa-miR-1261	-0.26	MS00014336	MSY0005913	MIN0005913	IGF1
hsa-miR-1264	-0.40	MS00014357	MSY0005791	MIN0005791	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-1266-5p	-0.28	MS00014371	MSY0005920	MIN0005920	MMP14
hsa-miR-127-5p	-0.28	MS00008575	MSY0004604	MIN0004604	NRP1
hsa-miR-1271-5p	-0.41	MS00014399	MSY0005796	MIN0005796	FN1
hsa-miR-1275	-0.45	MS00037786	MSY0005929	MIN0005929	IGF1
hsa-miR-1279	-0.47	MS00014448	MSY0005937	MIN0005937	NRP1
hsa-miR-128-3p	-0.06	MS00008582	MSY0000424	MIN0000424	IGF1
hsa-miR-1283	-0.26	MS00031353	MSY0005799	MIN0005799	IGF1
hsa-miR-1285-3p	-0.30	MS00031367	MSY0005876	MIN0005876	NRP1
hsa-miR-129-2-3p	0.00	MS00008596	MSY0004605	MIN0004605	NRP1
hsa-miR-129-5p	-0.08	MS00006643	MSY0000242	MIN0000242	IGF1
hsa-miR-1298-5p	-0.18	MS00014574	MSY0005800	MIN0005800	TGFA
hsa-miR-1299	-0.14	MS00014581	MSY0005887	MIN0005887	PTGS1
hsa-miR-1305	-0.15	MS00031402	MSY0005893	MIN0005893	IGF1
hsa-miR-1323	-0.49	MS00014658	MSY0005795	MIN0005795	CXCL6
hsa-miR-1324	-0.15	MS00014665	MSY0005956	MIN0005956	IGF1
hsa-miR-133a-3p	-0.17	MS00031423	MSY0000427	MIN0000427	MMP14
hsa-miR-133b	-0.17	MS00031430	MSY0000770	MIN0000770	MMP14
hsa-miR-135a-5p	-0.41	MS00008624	MSY0000428	MIN0000428	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-135b-5p	-0.41	MS00003472	MSY0000758	MIN0000758	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-139-5p	-0.23	MS00003493	MSY0000250	MIN0000250	THBS1
hsa-miR-140-3p	-0.25	MS00008673	MSY0004597	MIN0004597	TGFA
hsa-miR-142-5p	-0.30	MS00006671	MSY0000433	MIN0000433	IGF1
hsa-miR-143-3p	-0.22	MS00003514	MSY0000435	MIN0000435	PLAU
hsa-miR-145-5p	-0.48	MS00003528	MSY0000437	MIN0000437	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-149-5p	-0.11	MS00003570	MSY0000450	MIN0000450	PGF
hsa-miR-150-5p	-0.23	MS00003577	MSY0000451	MIN0000451	MMP14
hsa-miR-15a-5p	-0.08	MS00003178	MSY0000068	MIN0000068	IGF1
hsa-miR-15b-5p	-0.08	MS00008792	MSY0000417	MIN0000417	IGF1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-16-5p	-0.10	MS00031493	MSY0000069	MIN0000069	IGF1
hsa-miR-1825	-0.07	MS00014672	MSY0006765	MIN0006765	NRP1
hsa-miR-18a-5p	-0.22	MS00031514	MSY0000072	MIN0000072	IGF1
hsa-miR-18b-5p	-0.22	MS00031521	MSY0001412	MIN0001412	IGF1
hsa-miR-190a-5p	-0.19	MS00008911	MSY0000458	MIN0000458	IGF1
hsa-miR-190b	-0.21	MS00008918	MSY0004929	MIN0004929	IGF1
hsa-miR-192-5p	-0.22	MS00003689	MSY0000222	MIN0000222	IGF1
hsa-miR-195-5p	-0.10	MS00003703	MSY0000461	MIN0000461	IGF1
hsa-miR-196a-5p	-0.03	MS00031563	MSY0000226	MIN0000226	IGF1
hsa-miR-196b-5p	-0.03	MS00031570	MSY0001080	MIN0001080	IGF1
hsa-miR-205-5p	-0.37	MS00003780	MSY0000266	MIN0000266	TGFA
hsa-miR-215-5p	-0.22	MS00003829	MSY0000272	MIN0000272	IGF1
hsa-miR-219a-1-3p	-0.26	MS00009128	MSY0004567	MIN0004567	FN1
hsa-miR-219a-2-3p	-0.19	MS00009135	MSY0004675	MIN0004675	IGF1
hsa-miR-22-3p	-0.23	MS00003220	MSY0000077	MIN0000077	PTGS1
hsa-miR-224-5p	-0.07	MS00003878	MSY0000281	MIN0000281	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-27a-3p	-0.09	MS00003241	MSY0000084	MIN0000084	IGF1
hsa-miR-27b-3p	-0.09	MS00031668	MSY0000419	MIN0000419	IGF1
hsa-miR-298	-0.07	MS00009275	MSY0004901	MIN0004901	IGF1
hsa-miR-30a-5p	-0.13	MS00007350	MSY0000087	MIN0000087	IGF1
hsa-miR-30b-5p	-0.12	MS00003276	MSY0000420	MIN0000420	IGF1
hsa-miR-30c-5p	-0.12	MS00009366	MSY0000244	MIN0000244	IGF1
hsa-miR-30d-5p	-0.13	MS00009387	MSY0000245	MIN0000245	IGF1
hsa-miR-30e-5p	-0.13	MS00009401	MSY0000692	MIN0000692	IGF1
hsa-miR-323a-3p	-0.25	MS00037219	MSY0000755	MIN0000755	MMP14
hsa-miR-330-3p	-0.15	MS00031738	MSY0000751	MIN0000751	FIGF
hsa-miR-335-5p	-0.14	MS00003976	MSY0000765	MIN0000765	PGF
hsa-miR-338-5p	-0.30	MS00009478	MSY0004701	MIN0004701	NRP1
hsa-miR-340-5p	-0.16	MS00031759	MSY0004692	MIN0004692	IGF1
hsa-miR-34b-3p	-0.20	MS00008190	MSY0004676	MIN0004676	TGFA
hsa-miR-361-5p	-0.29	MS00004032	MSY0000703	MIN0000703	IGF1
hsa-miR-376a-3p	-0.35	MS00007392	MSY0000729	MIN0000729	NRP1
hsa-miR-376b-3p	-0.35	MS00007399	MSY0002172	MIN0002172	NRP1
hsa-miR-380-3p	-0.30	MS00006881	MSY0000735	MIN0000735	IGF1
hsa-miR-424-5p	-0.08	MS00004186	MSY0001341	MIN0001341	IGF1
hsa-miR-425-5p	-0.50	MS00009695	MSY0003393	MIN0003393	IGF1
hsa-miR-432-5p	-0.17	MS00031850	MSY0002814	MIN0002814	FN1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-450b-5p	-0.29	MS00033831	MSY0004909	MIN0004909	IGF1
hsa-miR-452-5p	-0.31	MS00031871	MSY0001635	MIN0001635	IGF1
hsa-miR-484	-0.18	MS00004277	MSY0002174	MIN0002174	MMP14
hsa-miR-485-5p	-0.12	MS00006972	MSY0002175	MIN0002175	MMP14
hsa-miR-486-5p	-0.20	MS00004284	MSY0002177	MIN0002177	IGF1
hsa-miR-488-3p	-0.15	MS00009772	MSY0004763	MIN0004763	IGF1
hsa-miR-497-5p	-0.08	MS00004361	MSY0002820	MIN0002820	IGF1
hsa-miR-503-5p	-0.26	MS00033838	MSY0002874	MIN0002874	IGF1
hsa-miR-504-5p	-0.15	MS00004410	MSY0002875	MIN0002875	PTGS1
hsa-miR-508-5p	-0.14	MS00009870	MSY0004778	MIN0004778	IGF1
hsa-miR-511-5p	-0.29	MS00006993	MSY0002808	MIN0002808	FN1
hsa-miR-513a-3p	-0.10	MS00009905	MSY0004777	MIN0004777	IGF1
hsa-miR-513a-5p	-0.10	MS00009912	MSY0002877	MIN0002877	IGF1
hsa-miR-513c-5p	-0.05	MS00009926	MSY0005789	MIN0005789	IGF1
hsa-miR-543	-0.39	MS00010080	MSY0004954	MIN0004954	ANGPT2
hsa-miR-548a-5p	-0.31	MS00010108	MSY0004803	MIN0004803	IGF1
hsa-miR-548b-5p	-0.31	MS00010115	MSY0004798	MIN0004798	IGF1
hsa-miR-548c-5p	-0.31	MS00010129	MSY0004806	MIN0004806	IGF1
hsa-miR-548d-5p	-0.31	MS00010136	MSY0004812	MIN0004812	IGF1
hsa-miR-548h-5p	-0.31	MS00014756	MSY0005928	MIN0005928	IGF1
hsa-miR-548i	-0.31	MS00014763	MSY0005935	MIN0005935	IGF1
hsa-miR-548j-5p	-0.31	MS00014770	MSY0005875	MIN0005875	IGF1
hsa-miR-548o-3p	-0.49	MS00014805	MSY0005919	MIN0005919	CXCL6
hsa-miR-548p	-0.11	MS00042413	MSY0005934	MIN0005934	IGF1
hsa-miR-559	-0.32	MS00010185	MSY0003223	MIN0003223	IGF1
hsa-miR-573	-0.04	MS00004781	MSY0003238	MIN0003238	IGF1
hsa-miR-575	-0.20	MS00004795	MSY0003240	MIN0003240	NRP1
hsa-miR-576-5p	-0.19	MS00007798	MSY0003241	MIN0003241	IGF1
hsa-miR-577	0.01	MS00004809	MSY0003242	MIN0003242	IGF1
hsa-miR-580-3p	-0.28	MS00010227	MSY0003245	MIN0003245	NRP1
hsa-miR-582-5p	-0.39	MS00004844	MSY0003247	MIN0003247	NRP1
hsa-miR-586	-0.14	MS00010248	MSY0003252	MIN0003252	IGF1
hsa-miR-588	-0.11	MS00004886	MSY0003255	MIN0003255	IGF1
hsa-miR-600	-0.30	MS00004963	MSY0003268	MIN0003268	THBS1
hsa-miR-609	-0.39	MS00005026	MSY0003277	MIN0003277	NOTCH4
hsa-miR-612	-0.30	MS00005047	MSY0003280	MIN0003280	NRP1
hsa-miR-618	-0.36	MS00005089	MSY0003287	MIN0003287	THBS1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-625-5p	-0.42	MS00033894	MSY0003294	MIN0003294	IGF1
hsa-miR-628-3p	-0.29	MS00005159	MSY0003297	MIN0003297	NRP1
hsa-miR-629-5p	-0.23	MS00010395	MSY0004810	MIN0004810	IGF1
hsa-miR-634	-0.22	MS00005201	MSY0003304	MIN0003304	NRP1
hsa-miR-646	-0.09	MS00032074	MSY0003316	MIN0003316	IGF1
hsa-miR-648	-0.31	MS00032081	MSY0003318	MIN0003318	THBS1
hsa-miR-766-3p	-0.16	MS00005439	MSY0003888	MIN0003888	IGF1
hsa-miR-767-5p	-0.28	MS00007182	MSY0003882	MIN0003882	IGF1
hsa-miR-891b	-0.15	MS00010731	MSY0004913	MIN0004913	FIGF
hsa-miR-922	-0.10	MS00010773	MSY0004972	MIN0004972	PGF
hsa-miR-936	-0.24	MS00032151	MSY0004979	MIN0004979	IGF1
hsa-miR-940	-0.12	MS00037688	MSY0004983	MIN0004983	IGF1
hsa-miR-942-5p	-0.35	MS00010885	MSY0004985	MIN0004985	TGFA
hsa-miR-96-5p	-0.41	MS00003360	MSY0000095	MIN0000095	FN1

Genes Over-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value
A06	ANPEP	2.30	0.000174
A07	ADGRB1	2.11	0.041037
A12	COL4A3	2.64	0.009831
B03	CXCL10	2.41	0.000007
B06	CXCL9	4.47	0.000405
C03	FGF1	2.34	0.025053
C05	FGFR3	2.76	0.000092
C12	ID1	2.32	0.000000
D02	IFNG	2.34	0.025053
D11	LECT1	2.34	0.025053
E05	NOS3	3.76	0.003773
F02	PLG	2.34	0.025053
F03	PROK2	2.34	0.025053
G10	VEGFA	8.23	0.003096

miRNA Regulating Genes Over-Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-579-3p	-0.09	MS00007805	MSY0003244	MIN0003244	COL4A3,VEGFA,FGF1
hsa-miR-29a-3p	-0.08	MS00003262	MSY0000086	MIN0000086	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-29b-3p	-0.08	MS00006566	MSY0000100	MIN0000100	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-29c-3p	-0.08	MS00003269	MSY0000681	MIN0000681	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-1	-0.12	MS00008358	MSY0000416	MIN0000416	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-106a-5p	-0.11	MS00029274	MSY0000103	MIN0000103	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-106b-5p	-0.13	MS00003402	MSY0000680	MIN0000680	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-125a-5p	-0.30	MS00003423	MSY0000443	MIN0000443	COL4A3,ANPEP
hsa-miR-125b-5p	-0.29	MS00006629	MSY0000423	MIN0000423	COL4A3,ANPEP
hsa-miR-15a-5p	-0.14	MS00003178	MSY0000068	MIN0000068	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-15b-5p	-0.14	MS00008792	MSY0000417	MIN0000417	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-16-5p	-0.09	MS00031493	MSY0000069	MIN0000069	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-17-5p	-0.11	MS00029274	MSY0000070	MIN0000070	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-195-5p	-0.09	MS00003703	MSY0000461	MIN0000461	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-200b-3p	-0.23	MS00009016	MSY0000318	MIN0000318	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-200c-3p	-0.23	MS00003752	MSY0000617	MIN0000617	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-206	-0.12	MS00003787	MSY0000462	MIN0000462	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-20a-5p	-0.11	MS00003199	MSY0000075	MIN0000075	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-20b-5p	-0.11	MS00003206	MSY0001413	MIN0001413	COL4A3,VEGFA

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-300	-0.18	MS00031689	MSY0004903	MIN0004903	ID1,FGF1
hsa-miR-381-3p	-0.22	MS00004116	MSY0000736	MIN0000736	ID1,FGF1
hsa-miR-424-5p	-0.11	MS00004186	MSY0001341	MIN0001341	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-429	-0.24	MS00004193	MSY0001536	MIN0001536	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-497-5p	-0.14	MS00004361	MSY0002820	MIN0002820	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-503-5p	-0.11	MS00033838	MSY0002874	MIN0002874	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-519d-3p	-0.11	MS00004508	MSY0002853	MIN0002853	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-548a-3p	-0.02	MS00033887	MSY0003251	MIN0003251	VEGFA,FGFR3
hsa-miR-548d-3p	-0.17	MS00007161	MSY0003323	MIN0003323	VEGFA,FGFR3
hsa-miR-548e-3p	-0.02	MS00014735	MSY0005874	MIN0005874	VEGFA,FGFR3
hsa-miR-548f-3p	-0.02	MS00014742	MSY0005895	MIN0005895	VEGFA,FGFR3
hsa-miR-576-5p	-0.36	MS00007798	MSY0003241	MIN0003241	VEGFA,FGF1
hsa-miR-613	-0.15	MS00005054	MSY0003281	MIN0003281	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-646	-0.13	MS00032074	MSY0003316	MIN0003316	CXCL10,VEGFA
hsa-miR-93-5p	-0.11	MS00003346	MSY0000093	MIN0000093	COL4A3,VEGFA
hsa-miR-338-5p	-0.19	MS00009478	MSY0004701	MIN0004701	ID1
hsa-miR-100-5p	-0.32	MS00031234	MSY0000098	MIN0000098	FGFR3
hsa-miR-101-3p	-0.54	MS00008372	MSY0000099	MIN0000099	PROK2
hsa-miR-122-5p	-0.09	MS00003416	MSY0000421	MIN0000421	FGF1
hsa-miR-1224-5p	-0.09	MS00008442	MSY0005458	MIN0005458	FGF1
hsa-miR-1238-3p	-0.20	MS00031297	MSY0005593	MIN0005593	ID1
hsa-miR-1253	-0.14	MS00014273	MSY0005904	MIN0005904	ID1
hsa-miR-1271-5p	-0.49	MS00014399	MSY0005796	MIN0005796	PROK2
hsa-miR-1299	-0.29	MS00014581	MSY0005887	MIN0005887	COL4A3
hsa-miR-1303	-0.51	MS00031388	MSY0005891	MIN0005891	NOS3
hsa-miR-1323	-0.10	MS00014658	MSY0005795	MIN0005795	FGFR3
hsa-miR-133a-3p	-0.32	MS00031423	MSY0000427	MIN0000427	FGF1
hsa-miR-133b	-0.32	MS00031430	MSY0000770	MIN0000770	FGF1
hsa-miR-135a-5p	-0.31	MS00008624	MSY0000428	MIN0000428	COL4A3
hsa-miR-135b-5p	-0.31	MS00003472	MSY0000758	MIN0000758	COL4A3
hsa-miR-140-5p	-0.24	MS00003500	MSY0000431	MIN0000431	VEGFA
hsa-miR-143-3p	-0.29	MS00003514	MSY0000435	MIN0000435	FGF1
hsa-miR-181a-5p	-0.02	MS00008827	MSY0000256	MIN0000256	FGFR3
hsa-miR-181b-5p	-0.02	MS00006699	MSY0000257	MIN0000257	FGFR3
hsa-miR-181c-5p	-0.01	MS00008841	MSY0000258	MIN0000258	FGFR3
hsa-miR-181d-5p	-0.02	MS00031500	MSY0002821	MIN0002821	FGFR3
hsa-miR-1825	-0.12	MS00014672	MSY0006765	MIN0006765	VEGFA

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-185-5p	-0.33	MS00003647	MSY0000455	MIN0000455	VEGFA
hsa-miR-186-5p	-0.41	MS00003654	MSY0000456	MIN0000456	VEGFA
hsa-miR-199a-5p	-0.15	MS00006741	MSY0000231	MIN0000231	VEGFA
hsa-miR-199b-5p	-0.15	MS00003731	MSY0000263	MIN0000263	VEGFA
hsa-miR-203a	-0.20	MS00003766	MSY0000264	MIN0000264	VEGFA
hsa-miR-205-5p	-0.40	MS00003780	MSY0000266	MIN0000266	VEGFA
hsa-miR-208a-3p	-0.06	MS00003794	MSY0000241	MIN0000241	COL4A3
hsa-miR-208b-3p	-0.06	MS00009058	MSY0004960	MIN0004960	COL4A3
hsa-miR-21-5p	-0.44	MS00009079	MSY0000076	MIN0000076	FGF1
hsa-miR-23a-3p	-0.38	MS00031633	MSY0000078	MIN0000078	PROK2
hsa-miR-23b-3p	-0.38	MS00031647	MSY0000418	MIN0000418	PROK2
hsa-miR-24-3p	-0.06	MS00006552	MSY0000080	MIN0000080	FGFR3
hsa-miR-27a-3p	-0.27	MS00003241	MSY0000084	MIN0000084	FGF1
hsa-miR-27b-3p	-0.27	MS00031668	MSY0000419	MIN0000419	FGF1
hsa-miR-296-5p	-0.38	MS00016401	MSY0000690	MIN0000690	CXCL10
hsa-miR-299-3p	-0.39	MS00031682	MSY0000687	MIN0000687	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302a-3p	-0.06	MS00009331	MSY0000684	MIN0000684	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302b-3p	-0.06	MS00003906	MSY0000715	MIN0000715	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302c-3p	-0.06	MS00003913	MSY0000717	MIN0000717	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302d-3p	-0.07	MS00003920	MSY0000718	MIN0000718	VEGFA
hsa-miR-302e	-0.09	MS00014693	MSY0005931	MIN0005931	VEGFA
hsa-miR-361-5p	-0.49	MS00004032	MSY0000703	MIN0000703	VEGFA
hsa-miR-369-3p	-0.19	MS00006853	MSY0000721	MIN0000721	PROK2
hsa-miR-372-3p	-0.07	MS00004067	MSY0000724	MIN0000724	VEGFA
hsa-miR-373-3p	-0.04	MS00031815	MSY0000726	MIN0000726	VEGFA
hsa-miR-374a-5p	-0.30	MS00009604	MSY0000727	MIN0000727	PROK2
hsa-miR-374b-5p	-0.27	MS00009618	MSY0004955	MIN0004955	PROK2
hsa-miR-377-3p	-0.11	MS00004095	MSY0000730	MIN0000730	VEGFA
hsa-miR-383-5p	-0.24	MS00004130	MSY0000738	MIN0000738	VEGFA
hsa-miR-410-3p	-0.08	MS00004144	MSY0002171	MIN0002171	VEGFA
hsa-miR-452-5p	-0.31	MS00031871	MSY0001635	MIN0001635	VEGFA
hsa-miR-484	-0.38	MS00004277	MSY0002174	MIN0002174	FGF1
hsa-miR-488-3p	-0.36	MS00009772	MSY0004763	MIN0004763	FGFR3
hsa-miR-495-3p	-0.20	MS00004347	MSY0002817	MIN0002817	ID1
hsa-miR-499a-5p	-0.07	MS00004375	MSY0002870	MIN0002870	COL4A3
hsa-miR-501-3p	-0.23	MS00009828	MSY0004774	MIN0004774	COL4A3
hsa-miR-502-3p	-0.23	MS00031927	MSY0004775	MIN0004775	COL4A3

miRNA Name	Strongest Strength Score	miScript Assay	miScript Mimic	miScript Inhibitor	Targeted Genes
hsa-miR-516b-5p	-0.18	MS00007749	MSY0002859	MIN0002859	FGF1
hsa-miR-519a-3p	-0.21	MS00033852	MSY0002869	MIN0002869	COL4A3
hsa-miR-519b-3p	-0.21	MS00004501	MSY0002837	MIN0002837	COL4A3
hsa-miR-519c-3p	-0.21	MS00010003	MSY0002832	MIN0002832	COL4A3
hsa-miR-520a-3p	-0.04	MS00004522	MSY0002834	MIN0002834	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520b	-0.09	MS00033859	MSY0002843	MIN0002843	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520c-3p	-0.09	MS00007413	MSY0002846	MIN0002846	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520d-3p	-0.04	MS00004529	MSY0002856	MIN0002856	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520e-5p	-0.10	MS00033866	MSY0002855	MIN0002855	FGFR3
hsa-miR-520e	-0.06	MS00004536	MSY0002825	MIN0002825	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520g-3p	-0.08	MS00031955	MSY0002858	MIN0002858	VEGFA
hsa-miR-520h	-0.08	MS00044926	MSY0002867	MIN0002867	VEGFA
hsa-miR-524-5p	-0.10	MS00031969	MSY0002849	MIN0002849	FGFR3
hsa-miR-543	-0.13	MS00010080	MSY0004954	MIN0004954	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548c-3p	-0.24	MS00010122	MSY0003285	MIN0003285	VEGFA
hsa-miR-548g-3p	-0.25	MS00014749	MSY0005912	MIN0005912	FGF1
hsa-miR-548m	-0.11	MS00031990	MSY0005917	MIN0005917	FGFR3
hsa-miR-548o-3p	-0.09	MS00014805	MSY0005919	MIN0005919	FGFR3
hsa-miR-548p	-0.39	MS00042413	MSY0005934	MIN0005934	VEGFA
hsa-miR-556-3p	-0.14	MS00032004	MSY0004793	MIN0004793	VEGFA
hsa-miR-569	-0.13	MS00010206	MSY0003234	MIN0003234	VEGFA
hsa-miR-570-3p	-0.48	MS00007791	MSY0003235	MIN0003235	CXCL10
hsa-miR-578	-0.52	MS00004816	MSY0003243	MIN0003243	VEGFA
hsa-miR-590-5p	-0.44	MS00004900	MSY0003258	MIN0003258	FGF1
hsa-miR-607	-0.27	MS00005012	MSY0003275	MIN0003275	IFNG
hsa-miR-621	-0.13	MS00005110	MSY0003290	MIN0003290	FGF1
hsa-miR-641	-0.23	MS00032067	MSY0003311	MIN0003311	COL4A3
hsa-miR-655-3p	-0.52	MS00010472	MSY0003331	MIN0003331	VEGFA
hsa-miR-656-3p	-0.23	MS00005355	MSY0003332	MIN0003332	IFNG
hsa-miR-760	-0.23	MS00037331	MSY0004957	MIN0004957	FGF1
hsa-miR-875-3p	-0.45	MS00010619	MSY0004923	MIN0004923	COL4A3
hsa-miR-885-5p	-0.45	MS00010668	MSY0004947	MIN0004947	PROK2
hsa-miR-889-3p	-0.44	MS00010710	MSY0004921	MIN0004921	VEGFA
hsa-miR-944	-0.19	MS00010899	MSY0004987	MIN0004987	VEGFA
hsa-miR-96-5p	-0.49	MS00003360	MSY0000095	MIN0000095	PROK2
hsa-miR-99a-5p	-0.32	MS00032158	MSY0000097	MIN0000097	FGFR3
hsa-miR-99b-5p	-0.32	MS00032165	MSY0000689	MIN0000689	FGFR3

Transcription Factor / Histone

Test Group	Control Group	Fold Regulation Threshold	p-Value Threshold
Group 2	Group 1	2	0.05

Genes Differentially Expressed in Group 2 vs. Group 1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	EpiTect ChIP qPCR Assay	Transcription Factors
A06	ANPEP	2.3	0.000174	GPH1018605(-)01A	MAZR, MZF-1, RP58
A07	ADGRB1	2.11	0.041037	GPH1012831(-)01A	NRSF form 2, NRSF form 1
A12	COL4A3	2.64	0.009831	GPH1008091(-)01A	IRF-2, deltaCREB, MyoD, Arnt, E47, Gfi-1, Pax-5, Zic1, Pbx1a, ER-alpha, Pax-4a, Evi-1, LHX3a/Lhx3a, FAC1, GATA-6, ZIC2/Zic2, CREB, CP2, GATA-1, LHX3b/Lhx3b, ISGF-3, Lmo2
B03	CXCL10	2.41	7e-06	GPH1023727(-)01A	NF-kappaB, IRF-2, NF-kappaB1, AML1a, NF-E2, c-Rel, IRF-1, NF-kappaB2, RelA, ISGF-3, NF-E2 p45, LCR-F1
B06	CXCL9	4.47	0.000405	GPH1023726(-)01A	FOXL1, CP1A, NF-YA, IRF-7A, NF-Y, HNF-3beta, CBF-A, NF-YC, FOXI1, HFH-3, CBF-C, NF-YB, CP1C, Gfi-1, CBF-B, Cdc5, CBF(2), POU6F1 (c2)
C03	FGF1	2.34	0.025053	GPH1024432(-)01A	Tal-1beta, SREBP-1a, SREBP-1c, Tal-1, SREBP-1b, E47, ITF-2, AREB6
C05	FGFR3	2.76	9.2e-05	GPH1009831(-)01A	Egr-2, HEN1, NF-1, NF-1/L
C12	ID1	2.32	0.0	GPH1008340(-)01A	USF2, TBP, Egr-1, CRE-BP1, AP-4, c-Jun, Meis-1a, deltaCREB, MyoD, Meis-1, USF-1, HSF1 (long), HEN1, Evi-1, ATF-2, CBF(2), ATF, NF-Y, STAT5A, AP-1, CREB, POU2F1a, LCR-F1, POU2F1, Egr-3, Meis-1b, c-Fos, Lmo2, USF-1:USF-2, HSF1short, USF1
D02	IFNG	2.34	0.025053	GPH1017290(-)01A	Nkx3-1 v2, Hlf, E4BP4, Nkx3-1 v4, GATA-1, MEF-2, AML1a, aMEF-2, MEF-2A, CREB, deltaCREB, Nkx3-1 v1, Nkx3-1 v3, ATF-2, Nkx3-1
D11	LECT1	2.34	0.025053	GPH1017697(-)01A	PPAR-gamma2, PPAR-gamma1, Pax-4a, MAZR, MZF-1, ARP-1
E05	NOS3	3.76	0.003773	GPH1012376(-)01A	PPAR-gamma2, GATA-1, PPAR-gamma1, SEF-1 (1), AP-1, c-Jun, c-Fos, FOXO1, FOXO1a
F02	PLG	2.34	0.025053	GPH1011694(-)01A	Pax-4a, HNF-1, POU3F2, HNF-1A, POU3F2 (N-Oct-5a), POU3F2 (N-Oct-5b)
F03	PROK2	2.34	0.025053	GPH1023115(-)01A	NF-AT1, p300, Tal-1beta, AhR, c-Myc, AP-4, NF-AT, RP58, Arnt, E47, Pax-5, USF-1, Max1, AML1a, Max, N-Myc, Tal-1, NF-AT3, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, SRF (504 AA), ITF-2, SRF, USF1
G10	VEGFA	8.23	0.003096	GPH1011376(-)01A	PPAR-gamma2, PPAR-gamma1, Hand1, COUP, Pax-4a, HTF, C/EBPalpha, AP-1, HNF-4alpha2, PPAR-alpha, CREB, XBP-1, deltaCREB, HNF-4alpha1, E47, COUP-TF, LyF-1, COUP-TF1
A02	ANG	-2.13	8e-06	GPH1003796(-)01A	nan
A04	ANGPT2	-2.64	3e-06	GPH1025988(-)01A	NF-AT1, RFX1, NF-AT3, Pbx1a, MIF-1, NF-AT2, ZIC2/Zic2, NF-AT4, SRF (504 AA), NF-AT, SRY, Gfi-1, p53, SRF
A09	CCL2	-33.55	1.5e-05	GPH1005667(-)01A	STAT5A, GR, C/EBPalpha, AML1a, GR-beta, STAT1, GR-alpha, STAT3, STAT5B, STAT1beta, STAT6, STAT1alpha, STAT2, STAT4
B02	CXCL1	-6.22	8e-06	GPH1010062(-)01A	NF-kappaB, TBP, NF-kappaB1, c-Rel, TFIIID, NF-kappaB2, RelA
B05	CXCL6	-9.41	1e-06	GPH1010059(-)01A	nan
C06	FIGF	-2.72	4e-06	GPH1027151(-)01A	POU2F2 (Oct-2.1), GATA-1, oct-B3, POU2F2C, NF-E2, Oct-B1, AP-1, POU2F2, c-Jun, c-Fos, POU2F1a, POU2F2B, Evi-1, oct-B2, NF-E2 p45, NF-1, POU2F1
C08	FN1	-2.23	4.3e-05	GPH1021782(-)01A	NF-YA, NF-kappaB, USF2, E4BP4, TBP, NF-kappaB1, E2F-1, AhR, C/EBPalpha, CBF-C, CRE-BP1, c-Jun, deltaCREB, NF-YB, E2F, Pax-5, AP-2alphaA, USF-1, Sp1, AP-2alpha isoform 3, NF-YC, USF-1:USF-2, ATF-2, NF-1, CBF(2), CP1A, ATF, NF-Y, CBF-A, Pax-2, AP-1, CREB, AP-2alpha, CP1C, Olf-1, C/EBPbeta, Hlf, AP-2alpha isoform 2, Pax-2a, c-Fos, SRF (504 AA), CBF-B, AP-2alpha isoform 4, SRF, USF1
D03	IGF1	-4.09	0.000441	GPH1017382(-)01A	ATF, Sox9, Meis-1b, aMEF-2, Sox5, AP-4, ATF-2, CRE-BP1, c-Jun, Meis-1a, SRY, MEF-2A, c-Myb, C/EBPbeta, Meis-1, Nkx5-1
D04	IL1B	-3.31	0.048571	GPH1021494(-)01A	NF-AT1, TBP, NF-AT3, TFIIID, c-Rel, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, RelA, NF-AT, C/EBPbeta
D05	IL6	-4.3	0.007952	GPH1011803(-)01A	NF-YA, NF-AT1, NF-kappaB, NF-kappaB1, GR, c-Rel, MAZR, c-Jun, NF-AT, deltaCREB, NF-YB, Fra-1, Pax-4a, NF-kappaB2, JunB, ATF-2, CBF(2), CP1A, ATF, NF-Y, CBF-A, GR-beta, AP-1, GR-alpha, CREB, JunD, NF-E2 p45, C/EBPbeta, LCR-F1, FosB, RREB-1, NF-AT3, NF-E2, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, c-Fos, RelA, CBF-B
D06	CXCL8	-11.41	0.0	GPH1010058(-)01A	C/EBPalpha
E02	MMP14	-2.63	8.2e-05	GPH1003823(-)01A	Tal-1beta, PPAR-gamma2, Pax-5, PPAR-gamma1, E2F-1, AML1a, En-1, ATF6, YY1, NCX/Ncx, CREB, MRF-2, deltaCREB, E2F, Egr-4, Nkx6-1, ITF-2
E06	NOTCH4	-2.8	1.9e-05	GPH1024831(-)01A	FosB, NF-kappaB, HOXA5, NF-kappaB1, GR, NF-E2, Bach2, GR-beta, NF-kappaB2, AP-1, GR-alpha, c-Jun, c-Fos, JunD, NF-E2 p45, JunB, Fra-1

Position	Gene Symbol	Fold Regulation	p-Value	EpiTect ChIP qPCR Assay	Transcription Factors
E07	NRP1	-2.78	0.003133	GPH1015632(-)01A	STAT1alpha, Sox9, E2F-1, STAT1, Sox5, STAT1beta, MyoD, E2F, Msx-1
E12	PGF	-2.52	0.000854	GPH1018061(-)01A	NF-AT1, NF-AT3, NF-kappaB1, NF-AT2, NF-AT4, NF-AT, MyoD
F01	PLAU	-2.33	6e-06	GPH1001684(-)01A	Sp1
F04	PTGS1	-2.22	1.8e-05	GPH1013260(-)01A	Sp1, TGIF
F08	SPHK1	-3.96	0.000161	GPH1006039(-)01A	Sp1, E2F-5, E2F-4, E2F-1, AhR, E2F-3a, YY1, Zic3, E2F, p53, E2F-2
F10	TGFA	-2.75	0.0	GPH1021322(-)01A	Sp1, Elk-1, Pax-4a, AREB6, c-Ets-1
F12	TGFB2	-26.16	0.002926	GPH1001266(-)01A	USF1, Max1, GATA-1, NF-kappaB1, c-Myc, C/EBPalpha, aMEF-2, Max, MEF-2A, Evi-1, Arnt, N-Myc, C/EBPbeta, USF-1
G02	THBS1	-5.35	0.000355	GPH1004398(-)01A	Sp1, Tal-1beta, GR, RSRFC4, AP-2beta, Tal-1, MEF-2A, GR-alpha, AP-2alphaA, CREB, AP-2alpha, deltaCREB, ZID, AP-2gamma, Roaz, E47, c-Myb, aMEF-2, ITF-2